

COMPLIMENT AS AN ENGLISH SPEECH ACT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6579934>

Annotation. The significance of this argument is that, despite the existence of countless works on the theory of speech acts and their classifications, the compliment remains understudied in all of its aspects. This thesis highlights the importance of studying a complement when learning English for mastering linguistic reality and obtaining communicative competence by speakers, and it examines the compliment speech act from the perspective of speech act theory.

Key words: speech acts, pragmatics, compliment, maxims, classification, complimentary statements.

Speech formation, or the replication of linguistic units in the process of communication, was primarily researched at the turn of the twentieth century when comparing speech to language as a potential system of signals for storing and sending information. In the 1960s and 1970s, scientists affiliated with the Oxford School (J. Austin, J. Searle, G.P. Grice) focused on the study of ordinary human language in its natural setting. Natural language's basic objective, according to these scientists, is to foster communication between people.

Speech acts are divided into various categories. J. Searle's traditional typology contains five classes: a) assertives (representatives), reporting on the state of circumstances and recommending a honest evaluation, b) directives, which motivate addressees to perform specific acts, c) commissives, which report on the speaker's duties, d) expressives, which express a certain psychological position in regard to any state of affairs, and e) declaratives, which construct a new state of affairs. (Searle 1986: 171).

J. Austin's classification includes: expositives (informative speech actions, communications), commissives (acts of accepting duties), behabitives (formulas of social etiquette), exercitives (acts of incentive), and verdictives (acts of establishment) (Austin 1986: 22-31).

A complement is an important aspect of proper communication. A complement is used in numerous speaking settings as a type of speech etiquette: at a meeting, farewell, congratulations, and so forth. It is critical that the interlocutors are aware of each other's speech acts in order to synchronize communication. If the interlocutors' speech actions are aware and purposeful, they may be analyzed in terms of the communicative code, which is a complicated set of principles that

govern both parties' speech behavior during a communicative act and is based on a set of categories and criteria.

The most important rules of communication are the Principle of Cooperation by P. Grice and the Principle of Politeness by J. Leach.

The essence of the Cooperation Principle is the obligation to provide a communicative contribution to verbal communication in line with the conversation's agreed-upon aim and direction. "Your communicative contribution at this level of the debate should be such as the jointly recognized purpose (direction) of this dialogue needs," Grice says. Four maxims comprise the cooperative principle:

- maxim of completeness of information;
- maxim of information quality;
- maxim of relevance;
- maxim of manners.

To begin, compliments can be categorised based on the features that are being commended, or the topic, trait, to which the complement is directed. Individual features of look, as well as portions of the body, might be praised for their attractiveness. Compliments on the following characteristics were recorded:

Eyes: "What nice eyes!"

Hair: "Your hair is special: dark, but with a golden tint. This is the first time I've seen such beautiful ones.

Hairstyle: "This hairstyle suits you".

Smile: "You have a nice smile".

Teeth: "You have beautiful teeth".

Figure: "Your body seems to me like the stem of the flower..."

Arms: "What pretty hands you've got!"

Legs: "Your legs are above all criticism!"

Neck: "You've really got a pretty neck, Jane."

There are also compliments regarding age. These include:

Understatement of age: "You look so young."

Compliments are also used to indicate adulthood.

"You have become very mature, Susan..."

There are also compliments indicating that the interlocutor has not changed, is not subject to age:

"You look absolutely unchanged

A complement, being one of the most common ways of making contact, cannot be analyzed without considering a people's language culture. The role of

the complement in theory of speech acts is not well defined, according to an analysis of the compliment speech act from the perspective of theory of speech acts. The speaking act of a complement is best assigned to expressives, as the study indicates, in terms of its major qualities. This viewpoint is supported by the principal function of a complement, which is to communicate a good judgment (assessment), as well as its linguistic characteristics (emotional-evaluative vocabulary). Because it is one of the fundamental components of speech etiquette, the complement is related with it.

The functional-semantic features of a compliment include vocabulary of a positive assessment: adjectives - nice, good ; nouns- beauty , angel ; verbs - to like , to love. The classification of complimentary statements is based on the intentional characteristics of the speakers, as well as the situation of communication.

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